

FIRE MODELLING OF MULTI-FUEL COMPOSITES WITH VARYING MATERIAL LAYERS USING COMPLEX STOICHIOMETRY

Debes Bhattacharyya¹

Imran Ali¹, Nam Kyeun Kim¹, Suresh G. Advani²

1 Centre for Advanced Materials Manufacturing & Design,
Department of Mechanical Engineering, The University of Auckland
New Zealand

2 Center for composite Materials, University of Delaware, USA

Centre for Advanced Materials Manufacturing and Design (CAMMD)

Based at Newmarket Campus

- Mechanical Engineering, Engineering Science, Polymer Science, Civil Engineering, Medicine, Sports Science, Architecture...

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Prof. Simon Bickerton

Mr Jos Geurts, Mr Callum Turnbull and Mr Stephen Cawley for their technical assistance

The Ministry of Business, Employment & Innovation, NZ for funding this research

PRESENTATION OUTLINE

- Background and Motivation
- Objective
- Manufacturing
- Test Methodology
- Computational Modelling
- Conclusions and Future Work

Source-servicemastersanfrancisco.com

Rise in research for sustainable flame retardant solutions

Fire Modelling

Source-profsharemarketresearch.com

Fire Testing Methods

Thermal analysis (~ mm)

➤ Thermogravimetric analysis

➤ Differential scanning calorimeter

(<http://archive.cnx.org>)

Bench-scale (~ cm)

Large-scale (~ m)

- Room corner test (ISO 9705)
- Single Burning Item test

(source: FTT)

(source: BASF)

UL-94 & Limiting Oxygen Index

TABLE X1.1 Materials Classifications^A

Criteria Conditions	V-0	V-1	V-2
Afterflame time for each individual specimen, t_1 or t_2	≤10 s	≤30 s	≤30 s
Total afterflame time for any condition set (t_1 plus t_2 for the five specimens)	≤50 s	≤250 s	≤250 s
Afterflame plus afterglow time for each individual specimen after the second flame application ($t_2 + t_3$)	≤30 s	≤60 s	≤60 s
Afterflame or afterglow of any specimen up to the holding clamp	No	No	No
Cotton indicator ignited by flaming particles or drops	No	No	Yes

- The minimum concentration of oxygen to support flaming combustion
- Specimen size:
 - 10 (width) x 150 (length) x 4 (thickness) mm
 - 20 (width) x 200 (length) x 0.1 (thickness) mm
- A supported specimen is ignited with a pilot flame, which then removed.
- Higher LOI, lower flammability

Flammability Characterization

Peak Heat Release Rate (PHRR)

Total Heat Release (THR)

Time To Ignition

Mass Loss

Co & Co₂ Productions

Smoke Production

Note: In the aviation industry, Ohio State University (OSU) calorimeter is used where the heating element and the specimen are in vertical positions.

Intumescent Fire Retardant Cycle

Intumescent APP
(condensed and gas phase)

Research Opportunities

Chemical Treatment Process of Wool Fibres

D. Jung, D. Bhattacharyya; ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng. (2018)
D. Jung, N. K. Kim, D. Bhattacharyya; Flame retardant keratinous fibre, WO 2018/070886 A1

Silicate coated Fire Retardant Chicken Feather Fibres for PP

(a)

↓ : Heating irradiance ↕ : Heat convection
↘ : Heat radiation ↓ : Heat conduction

(b)

— : Short flax fibre
↓ : Air flow

(a) At time to ignition, 25.5 s

(b) At time to ignition, 32 s

(c) At time to PHRR, 98 s

(d) At time to PHRR, 78 s

Thermophysical properties of the materials used in the numerical model

Property	Unit	Materials				
		PP	Flax	APP	Super wool	Char
Density	kg/m ³	900	1400	1900	64	550
Emissivity	-	0.97	0.85	0.94	0.9	0.93
Specific heat capacity	kJ/kg K	2.2	1.9	1.6	1.5	1.6
Thermal conductivity	W/m K	0.18	0.3	0.4	0.12	0.1
Heat of combustion	kJ/kg	4.9 × 10 ⁴	9300	-	-	-
Heat of reaction	kJ/kg	1987	1411	880	-	-
Reference temperature	°C	482	391	625	-	-
Heating rate	°C/min	20	20	20	-	-
Pyrolysis range	°C	155	145	400	-	-
Residue yield	kg/kg	0.2125	0.15	0.1	-	-
Number of reactions		1	1	1	-	1
Reaction order	-	3.2	1.7	3.2	-	-

Fire: A Complex Multi-Phase Phenomenon

- **Solid-phase pyrolysis:** Material decomposes, releasing gases.
- **Gas-phase combustion:** Gases burn, producing heat.
- Heat transfers back via **radiation, conduction, and convection.**
- **Dark zone above the sample surface:** Low temperature (<1000K), oxygen-free, drives pyrolysis.
- **Flame zone:** High temperature, gases combust.

Temperature Variation in the Gas Phase over the Burning Surface

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A photo of the flame and experimentally measured temperature variation in the gas phase over the burning surface of PMMA polymer showing the oxygen-free dark zone adjacent to the material surface.

Experimental setup

Flow diagram showing experimental data acquisition and its integration into FDS modelling.

The information acquired from experiments is used to define parameters in the FDS model:

Solid Phase Pyrolysis: Inputs include kinetic parameters, char residue, thermal conductivity, specific heat, heat of reaction, density, emissivity, and absorption coefficient.

Gas Phase Combustion: Inputs include combustion reactions, chemical species, effective heat of combustion, CO and soot yields, and boundary conditions.

- Treats composite as a **homogeneous fuel** source with a single global reaction.
- All volatile gases are combined into one **effective fuel mixture**, reacting in **one-step combustion**.
- Lower computational cost due to simplified reaction scheme.
- Does not capture layer-by-layer decomposition, limiting accuracy for multi-layered or sandwich structures.
- Appropriate for global HRR estimation, but less accurate for predicting localised burning or inter-layer dynamics.

- Solid-phase pyrolysis coupled with gas-phase combustion.
- Each composite constituent material undergoes distinct reactions.
- Tracks **species interactions** for precise combustion modelling.
- Enables **more accurate predictions** in multi-fuel systems.

(a) Cone calorimeter experiment

(b) Cone calorimeter model

(c) Temp contour at PHRR, 77 s

Solid phase pyrolysis (Anaerobic)

- Kinetic analysis using modified Coates Redfern - Kissinger method to derive kinetic parameters.

TGA simulation for Flax-PP composite with 15 wt% APP

Mechanism

Reaction

F-PP-15APP

(1) $PP \rightarrow 0.21 \text{ Char} + 0.79 \text{ PP (gas)}$

(2) $\text{Flax} \rightarrow 0.15 \text{ Char} + 0.85 \text{ Flax (gas)}$

(3) $APP \rightarrow 0.80 \text{ APP_Res1} + 0.20 \text{ APP (gas)}$

(4) $APP_Res1 \rightarrow 0.80 \text{ APP_Res2} + 0.20 \text{ APP (gas)}$

(5) $APP_Res2 \rightarrow 0.25 \text{ APP_Res3} + 0.75 \text{ APP (gas)}$

Gas phase combustion (Aerobic)

Stoichiometric chemical equations derived using MATLAB

Material	Gas	Stoichiometric chemical reaction
PP	Propylene	$C_3H_6 + 4.43435 (O_2 + 3.76 N_2) \rightarrow 2.9238 CO_2 + 0.024 CO + 0.058 C_{0.9}H_{0.1} + 2.9971 H_2O + 16.681396 N_2$
Flax	Methane	$CH_4 + 1.9861 (O_2 + 3.76 N_2) \rightarrow 0.98298 CO_2 + 0.0069 CO + 0.01125 C_{0.9}H_{0.1} + 1.9993 H_2O + 7.4677 N_2$
	Methanol	$CH_3OH + 1.4954 (O_2 + 3.76 N_2) \rightarrow 0.99433 CO_2 + 0.0023 CO + 0.00375 C_{0.9}H_{0.1} + 1.9998 H_2O + 5.6227 N_2$
APP	Ammonia	$4NH_3 + 3 (O_2 + 3.76 N_2) \rightarrow 6 H_2O + 13.28 N_2$

Cone calorimeter simulation for Flax-PP composite with 15 and 20 wt% APP

Applications of Complex Stoichiometry Modelling – multi-layered FR composites

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- Controls gas-phase reactions for each material.
- Enhances heat transfer prediction in layers.
- Stacking sequence impacts fire performance.
- Four distinct peaks in the HRR curve represent the sequential ignition and combustion of flax layers.
- The fourth peak, around 230 s, is less prominent but detectable, aligning with experimental results.
- Higher PHRR arises from flax's lower activation energy, leading to earlier combustion, while delayed PP-APP char formation later reduces HRR.
- FDS cannot simulate polymer melting and layer merging due to gravity.

Flax fabrics

FR-PP sheet

(a)

Sequence 1 (P/F/P/F)

(b)

Flax fabrics

FR-PP sheet

Applications of Complex Stoichiometry Modelling – multi-layered FR composites

Complex stoichiometry can track **individual species** during combustion

- Fuel species (C_3H_6 , CH_4 , CH_3OH , NH_3) concentrate near the surface – indicating onset of pyrolysis.
- CO and CO_2 levels are low.
- O_2 is uniformly available.
- Flame is surface-anchored with no significant plume yet.

At time to PHRR

(a) Fuel mixture

(b) Propylene

(c) Methane

(d) Methanol

(e) Ammonia

(f) Carbon dioxide

(g) Carbon monoxide

(h) Oxygen

(a) Fuel mixture

(b) Propylene

(c) Methane

(d) Methanol

(e) Ammonia

(f) Carbon dioxide

(g) Carbon monoxide

(h) Oxygen

At time to ignition

- CO and CO_2 levels are high - indicates intense combustion.
- Fuel gases spread further upward.
- Pyrolysis and gas reactions increase.
- O_2 is depleted near the flame showing high oxygen consumption.

Dark zone - sample undergoing anaerobic decomposition

Selected Publications in the Relevant Area

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- I Ali, N K Kim, S G Advani, D Bhattacharyya: Numerical models to predict fire behaviour of flax-polypropylene composites with intumescent flame-retardant; Applied Thermal Engineering, Vol 269, Part A (2025) 126008
- A Mishra, D Jung, NK Kim & D Bhattacharyya: Influence of chicken feather fibre processing technique on mechanical and fire performances of flame-retardant polypropylene composites; Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 165 (2023) 107338
- A Chanda, NK Kim & D Bhattacharyya: Effects of adhesive systems on the mechanical and fire-reaction properties of wood veneer laminates; Comp. Sci. & Technology, 230 (2022) 109331.
- A Chanda, N K Kim, W Wijaya, D Bhattacharyya: Fire reaction of sandwich panels with corrugated and honeycomb cores made from natural materials; Journal of Sandwich Structures & Materials 23 (8) (2021) 4196-4217.
- A Chanda, N K Kim, D Bhattacharyya: Manufacturing and characterisation of wood-veneer sandwich panels with flame-retardant composite cores; Composites Communications, 27 (2021) 100870.
- S Dutta, N K Kim, R Das, D Bhattacharyya: Evaluating Orientation Effects on the Fire Reaction Properties of Flax-Polypropylene Composites; Polymers, 13 (2021) 2586.
- Oisik Das, Nam Kyeun Kim, Mikael S Hedenqvist, Debes Bhattacharyya, Eva Johansson, Qiang Xu, Shima Holder: Naturally-occurring bromophenol to develop fire retardant gluten biopolymers; Journal of Cleaner Production, 243 (2020) 118552.
- N K Kim, F G Bruna, O Das, M S Hedenqvist, D Bhattacharyya: Fire-retardancy and mechanical performance of protein-based natural fibre-biopolymer composites; Composites Part C: Open Access 1, 100011 (2020).
- NK Kim, S Dutta, D Bhattacharyya: Heat and smoke production of flax fibre reinforced composites under horizontal and vertical orientations; Composites Part B: Engineering, Vol. 178 (2019) 1-12; Article 107467.
- S Dutta, N K Kim, R Das and D Bhattacharyya: Effects of sample orientation on the fire reaction properties of natural fibre composites; Composites – Part B: Engineering, Vol. 157 (2019) 195-206.
- S Dutta, N K Kim, R Das and D Bhattacharyya: A multi-physics framework model towards coupled fire-structure interaction for Flax/PP composite beams; Composites – Part B: Engineering, Vol. 157 (2019) 207-218.
- D Jung, I Persi and D Bhattacharyya: Synergistic Effects of Feather Fibers and Phosphorus Compound on Chemically Modified Chicken Feather/Polypropylene Composites; ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng., 7, 23 (2019) 19072-19080.
- D Jung and D Bhattacharyya: Combined effect of silicate coating and phosphate loading on the performance improvement of a keratinous fiber-based flame retardant; Chemical Engineering Journal 424 (2021) 130484.
- N K Kim, A Subasinghe and D Bhattacharyya: Natural Fibres: Their Composites and Flammability Characterizations; Ch. 4 in Multi-functionality of Polymer Composites: challenges and new solutions (ed. K Friedrich and U Brewer) Elsevier, Waltham, MA, USA (2015) 102-143.

THANK YOU